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COLOR IDENTITY IN TRADITIONAL CHINESE CULTURE

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ANNOTATION

Since ancient times, the Chinese have been looking for hidden deep meanings in everything that exists. The echoes of this quest can also be heard in the modern culture of mainland China, which, as many centuries ago, attaches great importance to symbolism. There are little-known cultural prejudices regarding the color that still lives in different sections of Chinese society, which from time to time remind themselves of themselves very vaguely ... For example: if you wear a green hat, then your wife is cheating on you!

Key word: color, Chinese culture, rainbow, traditional, history, yellow, green, blue, red, gold.

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XITOIY MADANIYATIDA RANGLARNING O'ZIGA XOSILIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Qadim zamonlardan beri xitoyliklar mavjud bo'lgan hamma narsada yashirin chuqur ma'nolarni qidirib kelishgan. Ushbu izlanishning aks-sadolarini ko'p asrlar oldin bo'lgani kabi ramziylikka katta ahamiyat beradigan materik Xitoyning zamonaviy madaniyatida ham eshitish mumkin. Xitoy jamiyatining turli qatlamlarida haligacha yashaydigan rangga nisbatan kam ma'lum bo'lgan madaniyat noto'g'ri qarashlar mavjud bo'lib, ular vaqti-vaqti bilan o'zlarini juda noaniq eslatib turadilar. Masalan: agar siz yashil shlyapa kiyib olsangiz, unda xotiningiz sizni aldayapkan bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Rang, Xitoy madaniyati, kamalak, an'anaviy, tarix, sariq, yashil, ko'k, qizil, oltin rang.

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ЦВЕТОВАЯ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТЬ В КИТАЙСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

С древних времен китайцы искали скрытые глубокие смыслы во всем сущем. Отголоски этих поисков можно услышать и в современной культуре материкового Китая, которая, как и много веков назад, придает большое значение символизму. Существуют малоизвестные культурные предрассудки относительно цвета, которые до сих пор живут в разных слоях китайского общества, которые время от времени весьма смутно напоминают о себе... Например: если вы носите зеленую шляпу, значит, ваша жена изменяет.

Ключевое слово: цвет, китайская культура, радуга, традиционная, история, желтый, зеленый, синий, красный, золотой цвет.

Chinese culture is one of the oldest in the world, in addition, it is one of the most developed cultures based on one polytheism. Like other states, it is not devoid of symbolism. The color scheme plays an important role in the transmission of information, for example, depending on the outfit of the official, it is possible to understand his career, social status.

The black border around the photo indicates that the person in the photo has died.

Or: a white gift wrap refers to an impending disaster.

As elsewhere in the World, colors are symbolic in China and can sometimes make you a bad joke if they are not used with enough attention.

In this article, we will consider the peculiarities of the perception of different colors of the Rainbow by modern Chinese society, we will try to explain the origin of cultural differences and give recommendations for those who are engaged in design work.

Red: most foreigners associate red with traditional Chinese culture, and this is usually true. However, there are nuances, especially for those who are engaged in packaging design.

In ancient China, Red was considered the color of fire. Unlike many other countries where fire has long been a symbol of danger and destruction, this element was generally considered good in China. Ajab not saying that the people of china: 红红, hóng hóng 火火, huǒ huǒ (hóng hóng, huǒ huǒ, literally "red, red, fire, fire"), that is, lifted up someone's life, continue to be heated, the red shine like flames.

In the same sense, 火了 (Huǒ Le, "fire") means that someone has achieved great popularity, while adjective 火爆 (Huǒ bào, "fire and explosion") refers to markets or crowded places that are crowded with people. interesting books or films.

Red has had these characteristics for thousands of years and today is a symbol of prosperity and happiness. It should be noted that red is the main color for holidays, especially New Year's holidays and wedding ceremonies.

Since the founding of the people's Republic of China in 1949, Red has represented communism, revolution and liberation, but it should be noted that this choice was made under the influence of the USSR, and Chairman Mao himself was strongly opposed to all kinds of prejudices. . So, do not confuse traditional Chinese red with political red - in ancient times it did not mean a revolution.

Advice to designers: it is good practice to use red to create Individual "Chinese" elements, but it should not be abused. The production of completely red marketing materials is the same as the constant packaging of goods with snowflakes in Santa Claus - pleasant for the holidays, but in mid - July it looks ridiculous-the Chinese (Lunnogo Novogo Goda) (春节) are used to the extensive use of red in the new year. The rest of the time, such a " triumph of colors " can be admired.

Yellow color: you need to be careful with this Color - its use in printed materials has its own meaning. Simply put, "yellow" is associated with pornographic material among Chinese, such as: 黄图 huáng tú (huáng tú, "yellow picture") means pornographic image, 黄片 huáng piàn (huáng piàn, "yellow clip") is an adult film, and finally, 黄网 huáng wǎng (huáng wǎng, "yellow web") porn sites.

Now that you see Chinese policyholders hanging “扫黄打非” (sǎo huáng dǎ fēi, “clean the Yellow, beat the Bad”), know that they are conducting the next raid against porn dealers and prostitutes.

Another major cultural meaning of yellow is its imperial purpose. Since ancient times, Yellow has been the color of Chinese rulers - remember about the legendary Yellow Emperor Huangdi: to say about a person 黄袍加身 huáng páo jiā Shēn (huáng páo jiā Shēn, wears yellow clothes) it is possible to know that this person ascended the throne, ruled power. The ancient emperors retained yellow for exclusive use, every stranger who dared to wear it was immediately condemned to death.

Advice to designers: avoid yellow in your products, beware of yellow in China. As a kind of trick, you can suggest applying the image of a dragon with five claws on a bright yellow background - a very strong, majestic sign, but not suitable for everyone.

Gold color: gold color has long been used in China as a symbol of nobility and wealth. It is closely related to the emperor - "bright, pure yellow".

Designer advice: for a Chinese audience, the use of gold in design is a great idea, in this case there are practically no restrictions and pitfalls. One thing - do not overdo it. At one time, the "Golden Rush" began in China - every merchant sculpted gold jewelry everywhere, thus devaluing and vulgarizing the color, which, if abused, looked cheap and tasteless. Rational use of gold paint is the best approach.

Purple: as in most European countries, purple in China is a symbol of nobility (but it has never been the color of rulers).

Unlike Europe, purple in China also has a deep religious meaning. The ancient Taoist symbol of divine existence is canonized as the "purple cloud coming from the East". The phrase is always used to refer to a dead object that has been immortalized.

Designer advice: purple can be successfully used to demonstrate the nobility and unchanging position of the brand, it has passed for centuries and remains immortal.

Green: while the Western idea of "Green" has similarities to the Chinese, there are subtle but significant differences that most foreigners do not understand.

In mainland China, green symbolizes purity, freedom from pollution and health. But this is not the cleanliness that is used to the West. When we talk about "green technologies", we mean environmentally friendly materials created for the benefit of Mother Nature.

However, in China, "green" vegetables do not contain pesticides, but the environment can even suffer from their production. "Green" milk is melamine-free milk that is harmful to humans. "Green" publications-materials that do not have prohibited content. As you can see, in China, "green" means a clear benefit for the consumer, but not for the environment-it is usually removed from brackets.

In general, Green is a good choice for painting any color (except hats). In the Celestial Empire, the "green hat" testifies to others that its owner has an unfaithful wife (in ancient China, the husbands of prostitutes wrapped a green scarf). When choosing gifts for the Chinese, green items of clothing should be avoided, especially if they are close to the head.

Green caps have become a special problem for ministers of the Catholic Church in China. Their coat of arms is traditionally made of a raised green headdress it uses, but in order not to lead to negative associations, it was replaced with purple.

Designer advice: Use Green for almost any marketing purposes, but do not hope that the ecological "green" meaning will be correctly perceived by the Chinese. And one more thing: if you don't want to become a laugh, never wear a green hat.

White color: unlike our mourning rituals, the Chinese use white instead of black. For example, 白包 Bái Bāo (Bái Bāo, "white envelope") - a white envelope with money to support the deceased's family - the opposite side of the red envelope-红包 hóng bāo - a gift for newlyweds and children. In addition, if a Chinese woman suddenly began to wear white jewelry on her hair, perhaps (but not exactly), someone in her family died.

Designer advice: white should be avoided when decorating festive occasions, even weddings, especially in less Europeanized areas of the country (where they make up the majority). Never wrap gifts in white wrap.

Black color: black on the printed throat has a wide range of meanings, such as evil, illness, injury, crime, greed. In the color palette, according to the Chinese people, it represents formality and seriousness.

The ancient Chinese regarded black as the king of flowers and respected him more than any other color, but black, like white, is completely unsuitable for decorating gifts, as it sometimes symbolizes death.

Designer advice: Try Not to overuse black. Never put black frames around photos of people, unless they are dead and are immortalized right now! In the same way, black and white photos remind the Chinese of the plaques on the graves.

Rainbow spectrum (rainbow color): the Chinese rarely use rainbow spectrum. The rainbow of the LGBT movement is unknown in China. The color spectrum in promotional materials is the third world by Chinese viewers it can be perceived as the flag of their state or even as printed inks of poor quality expired.

In ancient times, the appearance of a rainbow along the sun was considered a sign of the imminent death of the emperor or aggression towards his throne.

Designer tip: rainbows are ideal for decoration, but they are unlikely to cause resonance to the public.

Qing (Tsin): 青 qīng (qīng) is an interesting color that is not part of the standard set we are used to.

Some (including the Chinese) say it is blue, and some say it is green. In fact, somewhere in the middle of reality, and qing is more green-blue, bluish-green or something like that. In addition to this color, gray can be mixed, so green-gray-blue and other variations on the theme are acceptable.

The character of the color comes from the idea of the germination of the plant: qing means spring, energy and vitality.

Also, qing color is closely related to historical buildings and clothing-for example, there are qing colored bricks, and qing China is one of the color palettes of porcelain. In addition, Peking Opera has a type of female character called 青衣 qīng yī (qīng yī, "Qing colored costume") - this, as you might guess, is due to the blue-green dresses. Advice for a designer: do not forget about qing if it is necessary to express tradition, historicism.

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